

ISic2974

I.Sicily inscription 2974

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Catacomb 'Intagliata'

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175476

1. Μαρ-

2. κλανός.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494018

EDCS 39300427

PHI 175476

Bibliography

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